

A Bioanalytical Method Development and Validation of Metformin Using Piperine and Gallic Acid as Natural Bioenhancer

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ABSTRACT

The present research work highlights bioanalytical method development of anti-diabetic drug metformin using natural bio enhancer of piperine and gallic acid. The drug and bio enhancers were identified by applicable parameters as organoleptic, physicochemical and spectroscopical method. The RP-HPLC method is developed by simultaneous estimation of metformin, piperine and gallic acid using optimized mobile phase Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer 65:35. This method is validated as per ICH guidelines. A validated RP-HPLC method has been used for pharmacokinetics study of drug with natural bioenhancers using albino rat animal model. The different groups of animal which were previously treated with diabetic induced were again treated with antidiabetic and bioenhancer with minimum required doses. The plasma detection by RP-HPLC showed increased in AUC which indicated increase in C_{max} of anti-diabetic drug when given with bio enhancers. The developed and validated bioanalytical method is precise and accurate, can be used in pharmacokinetic studies.

Keywords: Natural bioenhancer, RP-HPLC, bioanalysis, Pharmacokinetics, metformin.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a type of metabolic condition characterized by prolonged increases in blood glucose. One of the largest public health dangers of the 21st century, diabetes is spreading quickly over the entire planet. According to the WHO, DM could overtake cancer as 2030; it will be the seventh greatest cause of death rates worldwide. Increased urbanization has contributed to the development of "Western" lifestyles in many emerging nations, which has led to greater intake of foods high in sugar and little physical activity. The high mortality rate of DM is caused by a lack of knowledge about it [1, 2, 3]

Once reaching the stomach, food reduces carbohydrates into glucose. When it initially enters the bloodstream, insulin release is triggered. After then by helping glucose leave the circulation and enter the body's cells, insulin reduces blood glucose levels. When a person has DM, insulin is unable to help

glucose reach the body's cells, resulting in hyperglycemia, or persistently high blood glucose levels. [4]

Our Ayurvedic literature has several remedies of herbal treatments, particularly those for uncommon illnesses. Almost 25% of pharmacopoeias now in use also list drugs with a botanical source. Many synthetic and natural medicines suffer from low absorption. Bioavailability is the rate and extent at which a chemical enters systemic circulation and becomes available at the required site of action. The maximum bioavailability is seen in drugs administered intravenously, while oral administration results in lesser bioavailability due to simple first pass metabolism and limited absorption. Such unutilized medicine in the body might have detrimental effects, including the development of drug resistance. Therefore, there is a need for substances that, although not alone having the same therapeutic effect, when combined with other drugs or chemicals boost their

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bioavailability. Many naturally occurring components included in medicinal plants have the capacity to improve the bioavailability of a medicine when administered concurrently. Bioenhancers are therefore chemical compounds that function to improve and increase the bioavailability of the medicines that are combined with them rather than having a synergistic effect with the treatment. [5, 6, 7]

The characterization of the pathophysiology of diseases and associated mechanisms of injury, the identification of drug targets, and the evaluation of novel therapeutic agents for toxicity/safety, pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and efficacy have all benefited from the use of animal models for drug discovery and development. The objective of the particular study will choose the particular animal model that is chosen to test and develop a certain medicine. Animal models are typically used in drug development to establish and offer evidence for non-clinical 'proof-of-concept' tests of the safety, effectiveness, and target of interest for particular pharmacological compounds. During the early stages of drug research and development as well as for eventual regulatory clearance for marketing and human use, determining safety and effectiveness metrics is crucial. In order to generate clinical forecasts of the anticipated outcomes in people, the use of animal models is also crucial. [8]

Drug development heavily relies on bioanalysis. Bioanalysis is a crucial component of pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic investigations, toxicological evaluation, and drug development. Bioanalytical method development is one of the bottle necks for drug development. For the quantitative measurement of numerous types of analytes in biological matrices, bioanalytical technique validation is also essential. Sampling, sample preparation, analysis, calibration, data review, and reporting are all steps in the bioanalysis process. [9]

EXPERIMENTAL

Drugs and chemicals:

Metformin (Sky remedies Mumbai), Piperine (Yucca enterprises Mumbai), Gallic Acid (Loba chemicals Mumbai), Acetonitrile (Merck life science Pvt. Ltd.,

Mumbai), Methanol (Shree Samarth Traders, Islampur) Double distilled water (Merck life science Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai).

Instruments:

UV spectrophotometer (Systronic PC based Double beam Spectrophotometer 2202), FTIR (Jasco FTIR 4600), RP-HPLC (Shimadzu- Prominence modular).

METHODS -----The procured drug sample was analyzed for its colour, odour, test and physical appearance, it was studied by visual inspection. Melting point was determined by Equiptronics melting/boiling point apparatus EQ 730. UV wavelength analyzed by using Systronic PC based Double beam Spectrophotometer 2202. The procured sample of Metformin, piperine and gallic acid was checked by carrying out IR studies. An IR spectrum of Metformin was recorded on FTIR 4600, Jasco, Japan.

RP-HPLC method development: [10]

The wavelength for detection was selected by preparing the individual solution of 20µg/mL of Metformin, Piperine and Gallic acid respectively. Each solution was scanned in the range of 200-400 nm and they were overlaid. The wavelength selected for the analysis 233 nm 345 nm and 217 nm respectively at which drugs showed significant absorbance.

Different mobile phases were tried in order to find best condition for separation of Metformin, Piperine and Gallic Acid. Mobile phase was prepared by Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer in the ratio of 65:35v/v. pH of mobile phase was adjusted to 7.0. Final chromatographic condition was obtained by using C18 column, 4.6x250mm, with mobile phase-acetonitrile: phosphate buffer 65:35 with 1.0 ml/min flow rate.

Sample preparation: Standard stock solution containing Metformin, Piperine and Gallic Acid was prepared by dissolving 10 mg in 100 mL of mobile phase and to get stock solution containing 100 µg/m. Suitable dilutions was made and the sample was filtered through 0.2 µ nylon membrane filter. [11]

The proposed method was validated as per ICH guidelines. The solution of the drug was prepared as per the earlier adopted procedure given in the experiment. [12]

Specificity: Specificity is a procedure to detect quantitatively the analyte in presence of component that may be expected to be present in the sample matrix. Specificity was measured as ability of the proposed method to obtain well separated peak for Metformin, Piperine and Gallic acid.

Linearity: The chromatograms of the resulting solutions were recorded and by observing the chromatogram if this appears to be linear relationship, then the test result was appropriate.

Accuracy: Accuracy of proposed method was ascertained on the basis of recovery study performed by standard addition method.

Precision: Precision of an analytical method is the degree of agreement among individual results when the method is applied repeatedly to multiple readings of a homogeneous sample. It is expressed as % R.S.D. of series of measurements. The interday and intraday precision was determined using 10 µg/mL concentration of drug.

LOD and LOQ: The LOD and LOQ were separately determined which is based on calibration curve. The S.D. of y intercept of regression line may be used as standard deviation.

Robustness: It is measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate change in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability in normal usage. The parameters for RP-HPLC method include the variation in flow rate, temperature, wavelength and mobile phase composition. The Retention time and asymmetry were considered for robustness.

Ruggedness: The ruggedness of an analytical method is the degree of reproducibility of test results obtained by the analysis of the same samples under a variety of conditions, such as different laboratories, different analysts, different instruments, different lots of reagents, different elapsed assay times, different assay temperature, different days, etc. Then each dilution of

the drug was injected and the chromatogram of the resulting solutions was recorded and further calculation was carried out.

Bioanalytical method development:

Animals:

Adult rat (250±250 g) of either sex were procured from the central animal house, Infinite biotech institute of research and analytics, Sangli and acclimated for a period of 7 days at room temperature. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee.

Preparation of drugs for animal treatment:

Metformin, piperine and gallic acid to be given orally, were dissolved in respective solvents and respective drug solutions were prepared.

Induction of diabetes:

After an overnight fast, rats were given a single dosage of alloxan monohydrate, dissolved in normal saline (150 mg/kg body weight, i.p.). The animals received regular pellets and water at will after receiving alloxan for an hour. The animals were stabilized for a week, and those with blood glucose levels greater than 6.0 Mmol/L or higher (200–300 mg/dl; mildly diabetic) as determined by a glucometer were chosen for the research. [13]

Experimental Design:

The “fasted” rats were divided into four groups, each group containing eight animals (n = 8):

Group: Control

Group I: Standard: Metformin (125 mg/kg)

Group II: Metformin and gallic acid (125 mg/kg + 10 mg/kg)

Group III: Metformin and piperine (125 mg/kg + 10 mg/kg)

Group IV: Metformin, piperine and gallic acid (125 mg/kg + 10 mg/kg + 10 mg/kg)

The drugs were administered orally to all animals in the four groups at the stipulated doses. The dosing was done in the same way. Samples were taken using the retro orbital method and plasma got separated from blood samples by centrifugation at 4000 rpm. At each blood sampling, appropriate eye care and antiseptic measures were followed.

A simple protein precipitate method was employed for metformin, piperine and gallic acid from rat plasma. A 100 μ L volume of plasma sample was transferred to a 1.5 mL plastic test tube, and then 100 μ L of the working concentration of the metformin, piperine and gallic acid was added to the test tube. After another 300 μ L of methanol was added for adequately precipitating protein, the sample mixture was vortexed for 1min and then centrifuged at 11000 rpm for 5 min to remove the protein precipitate. As aliquot of the supernatant was transferred to a clean glass tube and was evaporated to dryness under gentle nitrogen stream at 40°C. The dry residue was reconstituted in 100 μ L of the mobile phase and a 10 μ L aliquot of supernatant was analyzed by RP-HPLC.

Plasma samples were analyzed by RP-HPLC using validated method for the pharmacokinetic parameters. Pharmacokinetic parameters as C_{max}, T_{max} and AUC were determined using PK Solver software. [14, 15, 16]

Analysis of data statistically:

Data were represented as mean standard error of the mean, and PK Solver software was used for statistical analysis. The threshold for statistical significance was P 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

When dilute concentration of metformin, piperine and gallic acid were analysed by UV-spectrophotometer then it is found that, when concentration increases then absorbance also increases. Hence as per Beer Lambert's law the curve was found to be linear. Therefore these samples are UV detectable and can be subjected for bioanalytical method development by RP-HPLC.

Optimized Method:

Mobile phase composition- Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (65:35 v/v)

Flow rate: 1.0 ml/min

Wavelength: 233 nm for metformin, 345 for piperine and 217 for gallic acid.

Fig. no. 1: Optimized mobile phase - Acetonitrile: phosphate buffer (65:35 v/v)

<Peak Table>

PDA Ch1 233nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	Metformin	4.903	7728541	4175
Total			7728541	4175

PDA Ch2 217nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	Gallic acid	1.942	611954	3581
Total			611954	3581

PDA Ch3 345nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	Piperine	7.185	258249	3844
Total			258249	3844

Plasma Analysis by RP-HPLC:

Analysis of group-1

Fig. no. 2 Plasma analysis of group-1 after ½ hr.

<Peak Table>

Met 1/2hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm				
Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.012	12567481	4253
Total			12567481	4253

Fig. no. 3 Plasma analysis of group-1 after 1 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met 1hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm				
Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.396	10426855	4432
Total			10426855	4432

Fig. no. 4 Plasma analysis of group-1 after 2 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met 2hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm				
Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.951	9424577	4437
Total			9424577	4437

Fig. no. 5 Plasma analysis of group-2 after 1/2 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met+gallic 1/2hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm				
Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.231	13739531	4322
Total			13739531	4322

Fig. no. 6 Plasma analysis of group-2 after 1 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met+gallic 1hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm				
Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.159	14135238	4274
Total			14135238	4274

Fig. no. 7 Plasma analysis of group-2 after 2 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met+gallic 2hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.152	12245168	4168
Total			12245168	4168

Fig. no. 8 Plasma analysis of group-3 after 1/2 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met+piperine 1/2hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.751	17269070	4462
Total			17269070	4462

Fig. no. 9 Plasma analysis of group-3 after 1 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met+piperine 1hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	6.177	22333554	4356
Total			22333554	4356

Fig. no. 10 Plasma analysis of group-3 after 2 hr.

<Peak Table>

Met+piperine 2hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	5.884	20684238	4266
Total			20684238	4266

Fig. no. 11 Plasma analysis of group-4 after 1/2 hrs.

<Peak Table>

MPG 1/2hr.lcd

PDA Ch1 233nm

Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	5.881	34775653	3854
Total			34775653	3854

Fig. no. 12 Plasma analysis of group-4 after 1 hrs.

<Peak Table>

MPG 1hr.lcd				
PDA Ch1 233nm				
Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	8.032	23829426	4038
Total			23829426	4038

<Peak Table>

MPG 2hr.lcd				
PDA Ch1 233nm				
Peak#	Name	Ret. Time	Area	Plates
1	metformin	5.994	22245168	4156
Total			22245168	4156

Fig. no. 13 Plasma analysis of group-4 after 2 hrs.

Table: Pharmacokinetic parameters for metformin, piperine and Gallic acid in rat plasma after oral administration.

Pharmacokinetic Parameters	Group 1 Standard: Metformin	Group 2 Metformin + Gallic Acid	Group 3 Metformin + Piperine	Group 4 Metformin + Piperine + Gallic Acid
Cmax (ug/ml)	154.19	173.42	274.01	426.66
Tmax (h)	0.5	1	1	0.5
AUC mg*h/L	571.74	1470.67	1490.94	1643.70

The threshold for statistical significance was $P < 0.05$.

After oral administration of metformin in all groups remarkable increased in AUC at different time interval Cmax is found. This finding indicated that the systematic exposure (AUC) of pure drug significantly increases with given required dose of piperine and gallic acid.

In control group of animal when the plasma was analysed the chromatogram indicates a small peak is a baseline which may be due to previously treatment with alloxan monohydrate. In group-1 the plasma analysis of metformin by HPLC indicated sharp peak of metformin at R.T. 6.453 with area 10806304 (154 ug/ml Cmax). 31.25 mg/kg which was given orally to the albino rats of group 1.

In group 2, the pharmacokinetic pattern revealed that there is increased in AUC of metformin when the drug

was given with required amount of Gallic acid as bio enhancer. When the plasma collected of an interval of 0.5, 1, 2 hrs analyzed for pharmacokinetic pattern it is observed that there is increase in AUC which indicates increased in Cmax level. In group 3 the pharmacokinetic pattern revealed that there is increased in AUC of metformin more than group 2 when the drug was given with required amount of piperine as bio enhancer.

In group 4, when the plasma is analyzed with appropriate time interval then it is observed that AUC of metformin is increased with which revealed that increase in Cmax of metformin, means maximum amount of concentration of metformin is reached when given with required dose of piperine and gallic acid. Both bioenhancer act as synergistic effect which is confirmed in chromatogram by observing sharp peaks of metformin at R.T. 6.635. The peak of piperine is not seen in all groups after 1hr time interval

which may be postulated that the piperine will be quickly eliminated after facilitating the absorption of medicament. The fast absorption of medicament metformin may take place within 1/2hr after orally administration with bio enhancers together.

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